

MEDICAL SCIENCE

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FEATURES OF IMPLANTATION IN PATIENTS OF THE OLDER AGE GROUP

Abstract.

The priority direction of gerontology at the present stage is the issue of extending human life, but achieving this goal is directly related to improving the quality of life and health of people in older age groups. With the organization of the International Association of Gerontology (AIG) in 1983, the concept of "gerontostomatology" has become more widely used, the meaning of which is that the science of dentistry for people of considerable age is considered as a complex problem: first of all, as a discipline of dentistry, and also as a special part of gerontology [1].

Key words: age-related changes, features of implantation/

Numerous epidemiological studies conducted in foreign countries with a high level of dental care have revealed unsatisfactory oral health in older age groups. Among dental changes, the first place is taken by the loss of teeth with subsequent functional disorders [2-5]. Research data showed that from 21.4 to 64.2% of those examined had complete loss of teeth [6]; from 33 to 50% of those examined had problems with chewing food [7, 8]; from 15 to 30.8% experienced discomfort and were not satisfied with the condition of the oral cavity [9, 10]. According to other data [11], more than 62% of older people had one or more pathological symptoms in the oral cavity, and up to 30% felt somewhat socially isolated due to their oral health [7, 8]. About 15% of the examined patients with remaining teeth required urgent dental care [9]. From 69 to 90% of patients needed periodontal treatment, from 29 to 81.8% needed tooth extraction due to periodontal disease. And only 26 to 37% needed treatment of teeth affected by caries, most often filling only one cavity [7]. Danish scientists, during an epidemiological survey, identified a direct connection between the social and physical activity of patients and the condition of the oral cavity [16]. Among those examined (average age 67 years), only 10% led an active lifestyle, of which only 34% had complete absence of teeth, and among 36% of elderly people with low vital activity (5 diseases or more), 51% had no teeth. American and Japanese scientists are also of the opinion that physical impairment is a risk factor for oral diseases in the elderly and senile. The gender of elderly patients is also significant. Female patients tend to experience early tooth loss and seek dental care more often. Village women and housewives have higher rates of tooth loss and edentulism than those working outside the home. It should be expected that due to the increase in the number of elderly

people in the population, the proportion of elderly patients in dental treatment facilities will correspondingly increase. The professional activity of a dentist will be filled with this geriatric content. Moreover, this applies not only to orthopedic treatment due to tooth loss in old age, but also to preventive dental therapy for the growing number of elderly patients with natural teeth still remaining. It is natural that the organs and tissues of the oral cavity undergo significant morphological and physiological involutional changes during aging [8]. Many of these changes in themselves are not primary age-related changes, but secondary ones - due to functional disorders, diseases and bad habits. The most important changes in the maxillofacial system associated with age include: 1. Involutional changes in the oral mucosa and salivary glands 2. Diseases of the hard tissues of teeth and periodontal tissue 3. Loss of teeth 4. Manifestations of systemic diseases and side effects of medications in the oral cavity. Pain syndrome in the maxillofacial area (temporomandibular complex, etc.) The reaction of the salivary glands to processes occurring in the human body is a change in the amount of secretion and a qualitative change in its composition. It should be noted that dry mouth is primarily a consequence of systemic (general) diseases or exogenous factors - drug chemotherapy or radiotherapy. With age, the chemical composition of saliva changes significantly: for example, the amount of mucin increases while taking ptyalin, which is why saliva becomes more viscous and thick. Total protein concentration, alpha-amylase activity, as well as calcium and phosphate content remain unchanged in old age, and acidity decreases. Increased levels of lysozyme and amylase have been reported in the literature. Age-related changes in the salivary glands are characterized by a decrease in salivary ducts and an increase in adipose and connective tissue. Experiments on animals have proven that

protein synthesis by the salivary glands decreases by 60% with age. The general increase in the secretory concentration of IgA and the decrease in the concentration of IgG in saliva is not disputed by anyone, while higher and lower concentrations of IgM are indicated. This also applies to specific antibodies. As Percival studies have shown, IgA antibodies are increased for *S. mutans*, *A. viscosus* and *E. coli* in both general saliva and the parotid region, while IgG antibodies for *S. mutans* are significantly reduced. IgM antibody levels for *A. viscosus* were high in the oldest group of subjects. All these factors indicate a decrease in local immunity of the oral cavity in elderly patients. For patients of older age groups with reduced function of the salivary glands and poor oral hygiene, who use removable dentures, there is a high risk of candidiasis and other diseases of the oral mucosa. Due to the appearance of speech problems in these people, poor fixation of prostheses, and bad breath, social maladjustment develops. The chewing apparatus also undergoes significant changes as people age. The first signs of jaw involution - osteoporosis of the spongy substance and atrophy of the alveolar process (vertical and horizontal) - appear after 30 years, at 50-60 years the compact layer becomes thinner, after 60 years, due to tooth loss, these structures atrophy even more [9]. With senile atrophy of the alveolar process, protein transformation occurs primarily, and decalcification occurs secondary. Senile osteoporosis should be considered not as a disease, but as a manifestation of age-related changes in the bones. It is based on disturbances in protein and mineral (phosphorus, calcium) metabolism, with protein deficiency playing a major role. According to WHO, osteoporotic bone changes are detected in 15-50% of people over 55 years of age, while in 30% of those examined they are so pronounced that they can cause fractures of various bones. In long-livers, osteoporosis is detected in 100% of cases. Clinical decrease in height and decrease in thickness of the alveolar ridge are most pronounced with the loss of teeth, although they also occur in the presence of teeth and are accompanied by restructuring of the temporomandibular joint as a result of dysfunction, parafunction with symptoms of arthrosis or arthritis of the latter. Age-related morphofunctional changes also affect the hard tissues of teeth. A change in enamel color from white with a bluish or yellowish tint to yellow-brown is one of the external signs of aging. This is explained by the formation of a significant amount of secondary dentin, a decrease in the enamel layer and changes in the pulp. The color of teeth also directly depends on the degree of penetration of the coloring elements of saliva and food into the organic substances of the enamel [10]. Also, due to the long-term functioning of the tooth, its cavity narrows. The number of fibrous fibers in the dental pulp increases, which leads to sclerosis of the pulp and its degeneration into dense fibrous tissue. There is a decrease in the number of cellular elements and destruction of enzymes. In patients aged 60-70 years, the odontoblast layer still consists of 2-3 rows of cells, and at the age of 71-80 years, vacuolar degeneration and replacement of this layer with coarse fibrous tissue are noted [11]. In older people, petrifications of various sizes form in the pulp, the number of

vessels decreases, varicose veins appear, phlebitis and atherosclerosis develops. The cementum of teeth also undergoes changes in the form of cell layering and thickening, the number of layers directly depends on the load that the tooth undergoes. In elderly people it is 3 times thicker than in patients under the age of 17 years [12]. In elderly and senile people, the apical cement thickens and fuses with the alveolus, and the periodontal fissure narrows. The periodontium of the tooth plays the main protective, adaptive role to various loads when chewing food. The strength of the periodontium depends on the age, general health of the person, and the ratio of the length of the crown and the root of the tooth. With age, periodontal endurance decreases significantly, the circular ligament of the tooth degenerates and its connection with the root cement is disrupted. Physiological compensation for weakening of the periodontium is the abrasion of hard tooth tissues. Unfortunately, irrational prosthetic treatment of the dentition and failed dental restorations are often the cause of dental periodontal pathology, leading to pathological abrasion. Age-related progression of periodontal destruction is primarily a consequence of tooth loss and decreased gum level due to progressive bone loss. There is currently no evidence of a direct relationship between osteoporosis and periodontal diseases; moreover, age is not considered an etiological factor in the development of periodontal diseases and does not affect the outcome of treatment. Taken together, all of the above factors lead to tooth loss. Tooth loss is one of the signs of aging and leads to a significant decrease in the quality of life of a person of any age and especially of older age groups. Multiple or complete edentia leads to significant negative changes in appearance, speech impairment, and problems with eating. Against the background of other disorders in the body associated with aging, changes in emotional status are aggravated. Pain, fear, decreased ability to work, as well as negatively experienced changes in appearance significantly worsen the emotional and physiological quality of life of an elderly person. Recent changes in the age structure of society, the demographic forecast for the beginning of the third millennium and literature data give reason to believe that the issues of gerontostomatology are relevant and timely. Therefore, the strategy for providing comprehensive qualified dental care and the development of preventive measures for dental rehabilitation of people in older age groups should be carried out taking into account the variety of social and age-related problems. The purpose of the study is to analyze the long-term results of the functioning of dental implants and orthopedic restorations in patients of the older age group with various forms of edentia.

Materials and methods

During the period from 1994 to 2009, under our supervision there were 289 patients of the older age group (45-59 years) with various forms of edentia, in whom dental implants were used for dental rehabilitation. There were 125 men, 164 women. The patients had 3 forms of jaw edentia: complete - in 91 (31.5%), partial - in 138 (47.0%), single - in 60 (20.8%) people. The total number of implants installed in 289 patients was 1068. It should be noted that patients of the older

age group in terms of implantology and other types of dental treatment were one of the most motivated and informed, sensitive to the results of any stage of treatment, carefully following the doctor's recommendations and prescriptions. They adequately addressed the issues of oral hygiene and the need for dynamic monitoring of the state of osseointegration. They were the most selective in choosing dental implant systems, materials and methods of aesthetic and functional rehabilitation. Patients in this group could afford high-budget implant systems and high-tech prosthetic restorations based on bioinert alloys, all-ceramic (metal-free) fixed dentures. For many years, we have adhered to the principle that for patients of older age groups, oral sanitation, installation of implants, dental prosthetics and dynamic monitoring should be carried out by one dental specialist (implantologist). Results and discussion Of the 289 patients in the older age group who received complex treatment, complications were observed in 19 (6.6%) people. Complications were observed during the first year in 8 people, from 1 year to 7 years in 7 people, from 7 years and more in 4 people. Of these, 5 patients had complete edentia, 8 had partial edentia, and 6 had single edentia. Complications were observed in 2 patients with type I, 4 with type II, 5 with type III and 8 with type IV jaw bone architecture according to Misch and Judy. In total, in 19 patients, disintegration was observed in the area of 31 (2.9%) implants, of which 14 implants during the first year, 12 implants from 1 to 7 years, 5 implants from 7 to 15 years. Moreover, 14 of these implants were successfully reimplanted after revascularization and targeted tissue regeneration of bone using platelet-rich blood plasma. In 186 patients, the installation of implants was combined simultaneously with various osteoplastic measures. Osteoplastic, reconstructive surgical measures were carried out using a combination of bone-replacing and autobone materials and the use of barrier membranes for directed tissue regeneration (closure of fenestrated, slit-like, extended bone defects of the alveolar ridge, clefting, passive and active raising of the bottom of the maxillary sinus). These operations were performed in 89 patients with immediate (immediate) implantation, in 97 patients with delayed dental implantation. Loosening of screw fixation was observed in 14 patients, fracture of fixing screws in 4, and chipping of ceramic veneer in 11 patients.

Conclusions.

Thus, an analysis of our own clinical observations conducted over the past 15 years has shown the high effectiveness of the use of dental implants in the complex rehabilitation of patients in the older age group

with various forms of jaw edentia. This category of patients is the most disciplined and sensitive to the results of treatment. Together, in this group of patients, complications of dental implantation in the form of disintegration were brought to 6.6%. Consequently, in the absence of contraindications, a high degree of patient motivation, and proper planning of the stages of complex treatment, dental implantation can be successfully used for the aesthetic and functional rehabilitation of patients in the older age group with various forms of jaw edentia.

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